

OPTIMAL DIMENSIONING OF CORONA RING IN HIGH VOLTAGE INSULATOR STRING

DIMENSI OPTIMUM CINCIN KORONA DALAM RENTETAN PENEBAT VOLTAN TINGGI

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ABSTRACT

Every conductor used in high voltage electric transmission network is exposed and protected by the surrounding air causes the conductivity of the electric current through the conductor to not occur perfectly. However, using only insulation will also causes problems where corona discharges occurs due to air ionization (or any other liquid) surrounding the electrical conductor, as a result of a strong electric field. Due to the high intensity of electric field cause by corona discharges at an energized end at insulator string, it may cause a complete failure for it to well-functioning. The main aim of this project is to design an optimal dimension of corona ring to reduce electric field distribution at high voltage insulator string surface during normal operating condition. Designing a corona ring with an insulator string is to reduce the effect of corona discharges as well as intensity of electric field stress at the energized end at insulator string. The electric field analysis was done using COMSOL Multiphysics, a finite element based software used to design the insulator string with corona ring model by using Finite Element Method and MATLAB, a proprietary programming language software using its implementation of algorithms program to determine the optimal configuration of the corona ring by using Particle Swarm Optimization Method.

Keywords: Corona Discharge; High Voltage Insulator String; Corona Ring; Finite Element Method; Particle Swarm Optimization Method

ABSTRAK

Setiap konduktor yang digunakan dalam rangkaian penghantaran elektrik voltan tinggi terdedah dan dilindungi oleh udara di sekeliling menyebabkan kekonduksian arus elektrik melalui konduktor tidak berlaku dengan sempurna. Walau bagaimanapun, hanya menggunakan penebat juga akan menyebabkan masalah di mana nyahcas korona berlaku disebabkan pengionan udara (atau cecair lain) yang mengelilingi konduktor elektrik, hasil daripada medan elektrik yang kuat. Disebabkan oleh tekanan intensiti yang tinggi dari medan elektrik yang disebabkan oleh nyahcas korona pada konduktor elektrik pada hujung penebat, ia boleh menyebabkan kegagalan penebat untuk berfungsi dengan baik. Tujuan utama projek ini adalah untuk merekabentuk dimensi optimum cincin korona untuk mengurangkan pengagihan medan elektrik pada permukaan penebat voltan tinggi semasa keadaan operasi biasa. Merekabentuk cincin korona dengan penebat adalah untuk mengurangkan kesan nyahcas korona serta tekanan intensiti medan elektrik pada konduktor elektrik pada hujung penebat. Analisis medan elektrik dilakukan menggunakan COMSOL Multiphysics, sebuah perisian berasaskan elemen terhingga yang digunakan untuk merekabentuk model penebat voltan tinggi dengan cincin korona dengan menggunakan Analisis Unsur Terhingga dan MATLAB, perisian bahasa pengaturcaraan proprietari menggunakan pelaksanaan program algoritma untuk menentukan konfigurasi optimum cincin korona dengan menggunakan Teknik Pengoptimuman Kerumusan Zarah.

Kata kunci: Nyahcas Corona; Penebat Voltan Tinggi; Cincin Corona; Analisis Unsur Terhingga; Pengoptimum Kerumusan Zarah

INTRODUCTION

Electric is an important requirements for peoples to use electrical and electronic in this modern days. Life and daily activities are not smooth when there is a power supply system failure. The existence of electrical energy has a high impact on human facilities in daily activities. The industrial sector

needs electricity to produce effective electricity production. The supply of electricity needs to be through three stages namely the generation of electricity at power stations, transmission and distribution of electricity to consumers. The generation of electricity at the power station will be increased by voltage before being sent to the main entrance substation at the specified destination and

through the electricity transmission stage. Subsequently, the electricity delivered will be distributed to consumers during the electricity distribution stage. These three stages are important in supplying electricity to consumers. If one of the stages failed or damaged, the electric supply fails to deliver to the consumers.

This study is related to the second stage in supplying electricity which is the transmission of electricity to consumers. In the transmission stage of electricity, there are some main components required during transmission of electrical energy and each component has its own functionality to prevent the occurrence of electricity transmission failure to consumers. Insulation is one of the major components required in high voltage electric power transmission networks and also plays an important role as the insulation path between live conductors from electrical transmission and distribution towers. This high-voltage insulator helps separate live conductors from one another and from utility poles (Ammar al-Ghelani, 2016). Due to the flow of conductors exposed and resulting in flashover on the surface of the insulation occurs, especially when in wet or damp conditions, transmission of electricity to consumers will fail and interfere with the daily activities of the user.

There are three main types of insulating materials used in high voltage electric transmission systems i.e. glass, porcelain or polymer composite. Electrical Utility has changed the polymer composite material for some types of insulation such as insulation center rods made of overhead fiber plastic and outdoor weather shields made of silicon rubber as will be used in this study. Silicone rubber insulator or also known as composite insulator having many advantages such as good performance when pollution occurs around it due to its hydrophobic composite properties. Besides that, silicone rubber insulator is also lightweight, has low installation costs, easy to operate and requires little maintenance to ensure the insulator is in a good condition (Hackam R. 1999).

However, every conductor used in high voltage electric transmission network is exposed and protected by the surrounding air causes the conductivity of the electric current through the conductor to not occur perfectly. Using only insulation will also occur problems where corona discharges (light on conductors when high voltage) which occurs due to air ionization (or any other liquid) surrounding the electrical conductor, as a result of a strong electric field (Suat İlhan & Aydoğan Özdemir. 2011). Corona discharges occurs producing sizzling noise, visual violet light, surrounding ozone gas conductor, radio frequency interference, electrical energy loss and increasing electrical field magnitudes and failing power supply transmission. The electrical field magnitude and the voltage distributed over the insulation strap

due to the insulation material used and the resulting capacitance are not uniform causes the electrical field magnitude on the insulation units near the end of the insulation will increase (A. Rahimnejad & M. Mirzaie, 2012).

To reduce the magnitude of the electric field and improve the performance of high voltage insulation strings by reducing the corona discharge, the corona ring is designed (B. M'hamdi et al. 2015). Therefore, the optimum corona ring design is proposed to reduce the electric field magnitude on high voltage insulation. This also helps side effects due to corona discharges that occur on the insulation thus helping to reduce the potential for transmission failure of electricity to consumers. In addition, to produce optimum corona ring design requires a high cost when conducting research and testing if using a real prototype. Thus, computer equipped with relevant software is used to perform the operating ability, simulation and corona ring performance in the early stages before proceeding with the actual prototype construction reduces the cost of doing research and testing.

METHODOLOGY

After collecting all relevant information / theories, the design for high voltage insulation and optimal corona ring can be built. The design of high voltage insulator string and corona ring is built using COMSOL Multiphysics and optimized by MATLAB computer software by using the Finite Element Analysis and Particle Formula Optimizer alternately. The effects of high voltage insulation geometry and corona rings on the electric field distribution will be studied and compared to reach the objective of designing corona rings with optimum dimensions to maximize the reduction electric field magnitude.

Modeling of insulator string using FEM

The two-dimensional (2D) axial symmetry model geometry of 230kV Silicone Rubber insulator string with corona ring (FIGURE 1) was designed by FEM software using electrostatic as an interface of the AC/DC module available in the software to solve the model. As stated by A. Rahimnejad and M. Mirzae (2012), this FEM is the primary numerical calculation technique for calculating and optimizing insulation performance under the electromagnetic field. Due to these statements, this technique is to be used to design high voltage insulator string and corona rings in this study to achieve the main objective of reducing the electric field distribution over insulator string surface. The designed height of insulator string model is 2405mm with surrounding air around the insulator string was also drawn spherical around model to

observe electric field distribution on the surface of the insulator's sheds.

The uniformity degree of voltage distribution depends on insulator sheds capacitance, the number of sheds which designed in this model were 69 sheds overall consists of 35 outer sheds and 34 inner sheds and corona ring dimensions (E. Akbari & M. Mirzaie, 2012). Each domain was assigned with its material properties and each boundary in geometry was applied to relevant interface conditions. At upper part of insulator string, the ground boundary condition was applied with zero electric potential while at the bottom part of insulator string was applied as a terminal source of 230kV electric potential. Also, the boundaries of corona ring were applied as 230kV electric potential and the remaining boundaries of geometry were set as continuity.

According to B. M'hamdi et al. (2015), there are no specific standards for the design and position of corona ring. The designs were different from each manufacturer because they make their own recommendations for the use of corona rings. The optimization dimensions are the radius and

height of corona ring which is the position of corona ring from the center and from the bottom end of FRP rod respectively. However, the optimized value of these dimensions must reduce the electric field distribution along the insulator axis, which is located at the tip of first shed near to high voltage electrode of insulator string which is categorized as critical on insulator string. To avoid any surface discharge, the maximum electric field distribution on silicone rubber surface must be equal or less than the breakdown strength of silicone rubber around 30.00kV/mm to 40.00kV/mm and the maximum electric field distribution on air domain must be equal or less than breakdown strength of air, 3.00kV/mm. Table 2 below shows the different dimensions (in boundary range) of corona ring which was optimized to achieve the optimal dimensions of corona ring. To avoid impractical corona ring position in applications, the boundary ranges in this study are chosen for the feasibility region of corona ring is;

FIGURE 1. 2D asymmetry of Silicone Rubber insulator string with corona ring (circle) model

TABLE 1. Material properties of insulator string components

Domain	Components	Material	Relative permittivity, ϵ_r	Conductivity, σ (Sm ⁻¹)
1	Corona ring	Aluminum	1	3.774x10 ⁴
2	High voltage electrode			
3	Sheds of insulator string	Silicone rubber	4.3	1x10 ⁻¹⁸
4	Insulator rod	Fiberglass Reinforced Plastics	7.2	1x10 ⁻¹⁸
5	-	Air	1	0

TABLE 2. Initial dimensions of Corona Ring and range of boundary dimensions to optimization

Dimensions	Radius(mm)	Height(mm)
Initial value	185.00	131.15
Lower boundary	155.00	101.15
Upper boundary	205.00	151.15

Optimization dimensions using PSO

In Particle Swarm Optimization method, each particle tracks its coordinates in the problem surface associated with the best solution (output)

that has been reached is known as Pbest, (Local/Particle Best). Whereas, Gbest (Global Best) is obtained by the best comparison of Pbest particles that have been identified based on the

minimum output value which is in this study, the value of the output to be achieved is the minimum

electric field distribution value. The flowchart of PSO Method is shown in FIGURE 2.

FIGURE 2. Flowchart of Particle Swarm Optimization Method

RESULTS

FIGURE 3 shows the electric field distribution around 230kV potential energy at energized end insulator string surface (a) without corona ring, (b) applying corona ring with initial value of dimensions and (c) applying corona ring with optimum dimensions which were optimized using PSO techniques in this study during normal operation. The electric field magnitude around insulator string surface is high but reducing after applying a corona ring to insulator string. This shows that applying a corona ring can reduce the electric field distribution along the insulator string surface as well as reducing corona discharges and its effect during the discharges. The lowest electric field magnitude among the maximum electric field magnitude of electric field distribution of FIGURE 3 electric field distribution at insulator string surface was recorded from FIGURE 3b, 7.40kV/mm. After the implementation of PSO algorithm in the model, the results shows that there was a reduction of maximum electric field magnitude from insulator string applying with initial dimensions and after the optimization. This result also shows that the electric field distribution also depends on the dimensions of the corona ring.

FIGURE 4 shows the electric field distribution along the insulator outer sheds for as same application in FIGURE 3. Minor reduction on

the maximum electric field magnitude was occurred comparing both magnitudes after applying a corona ring in FIGURE 4. Discontinuity of the electric field between insulator's outer and inner sheds domain was observed due to difference in permittivity value of materials at 2D cut line which were assigned at outer sheds line. Masoud Jowkar et. Al (2011) mentioned that in electric field distribution, the electric field magnitude is high at the energized end at insulator string and reduces exponentially along the insulator length.

TABLE 3 presents the electric field magnitude at the tip of first shed near to high voltage electrode of insulator string obtained from insulator string without corona ring, with initial dimensions of corona ring and with optimized dimensions of corona ring. From TABLE 3, it can be seen that after the PSO optimization yield lower minimum electric field magnitude than the initial dimensions of corona ring which the percentage of reduction from electric field magnitude at the tip of the first shed near the energized end increase from 28.2726% by initial dimensions to 39.9060% by optimized dimensions of corona ring.

FIGURE 3. Electric field distribution along 230kV insulator string surface (a) without corona ring, (b) applying corona ring with initial value of dimensions and (c) applying corona ring with optimum parameters

FIGURE 4. Electric field distribution along outer sheds surface (a) without corona ring, (b) applying corona ring with initial value of dimensions and (c) applying corona ring with optimum parameters

TABLE 3. Electrical and insulation data of insulator.

Model	Radius of Corona Ring (mm)	Height of Corona Ring (mm)	Electric Field at tip of the first shed (kV/mm)	Reduction Electric Field from without Corona Ring(%)
Without Corona Ring	-	-	0.4255	-
Initial Corona Ring	185.0000	131.1500	0.3052	28.2726
PSO optimized	188.8491	121.7659	0.2557	39.9060

DISCUSSION

To understand the effect of difference dimensions of corona ring applied to 230kV insulator string, an attempt was done by designing a 2-D asymmetric

model using FEM and the materials and conditions of each component are taken into account. To overcome the results, as many as 20 iterations calculation of optimization by MATLAB had been

done and the program loop running for maximum 10 times to get the best optimized value of dimension corona ring with minimum value of electric field distribution.

CONCLUSION

According to the results, electric field distribution over insulator string with applying a corona ring depends on the position (parameters) of corona ring from the energized end at insulator string. It is wise to choose the suitable materials and its characteristic to use in simulation since it will give difference in electric field distribution result. By optimizing the dimensions of corona ring, the electric field intensity around the insulator string surface successfully reduced while maintaining its physical properties. The lowest concentration of the electric field around insulator string surface can be achieved as well as the life span of the insulator string.

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